

Design and Analysis Bridgeless Converter-Based Electric Vehicle Charger

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Abstract— The increasing adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) necessitates the development of efficient and reliable charging systems to support the transition to sustainable transportation. Traditional electric vehicle chargers often face challenges such as high-power losses, low efficiency, and significant electromagnetic interference (EMI) due to their complex circuit designs. This paper proposes the design and analysis of a bridgeless converter-based electric vehicle (EV) charger, aiming to overcome these limitations. The bridgeless topology eliminates the need for a traditional diode bridge rectifier, significantly reducing conduction losses and improving overall efficiency. Furthermore, the proposed charger incorporates power factor correction (PFC) to enhance grid compatibility and meet regulatory standards. Detailed simulations and experimental evaluations validate the performance of the designed system, demonstrating its capability to achieve high power density, improved thermal performance, and minimized harmonic distortion. This work provides a comprehensive understanding of the advantages of bridgeless converter-based EV chargers, contributing to the development of next-generation EV charging technologies.

Keywords—EV, Battery, Current, Voltage, Power, Flyback, AC-DC, DC-DC converter, power factor correction

I. INTRODUCTION

The global shift towards electrification in the automotive sector has created an urgent demand for efficient and sustainable charging solutions for electric vehicles (EVs). As EVs gain widespread popularity, the development of advanced charging infrastructures has become a key focus for researchers and industries alike. Traditional EV chargers, typically based on diode bridge rectifiers, suffer from significant drawbacks, including high power losses, limited efficiency, and increased thermal stress on components. These issues not only compromise the reliability of the charging system but also result in higher operational costs and environmental impact. To address these challenges, innovative converter topologies are required to enhance the efficiency and performance of EV chargers.

Among the various advanced topologies, bridgeless converters have emerged as a promising solution for improving the performance of EV charging systems. Unlike conventional designs, bridgeless converters eliminate the diode bridge rectifier, thereby reducing conduction losses and improving power conversion efficiency. Additionally, bridgeless designs inherently produce lower levels of electromagnetic interference (EMI) and exhibit superior

thermal management capabilities. These features make bridgeless converters particularly suitable for high-power applications such as EV chargers, where efficiency and reliability are paramount.

The proposed bridgeless converter-based EV charger incorporates power factor correction (PFC) to ensure compatibility with grid standards and to minimize the harmonic distortion typically associated with traditional charging systems. Power factor correction not only improves the quality of power drawn from the grid but also helps in reducing energy wastage and ensuring stable grid operation. This dual functionality of high efficiency and PFC compliance makes the bridgeless converter an attractive choice for modern EV charging systems.

The research begins with a comprehensive review of existing EV charging technologies, highlighting the limitations of traditional diode bridge rectifier-based systems and the need for innovative solutions. The bridgeless topology is then introduced, along with a detailed explanation of its working principles, advantages, and potential challenges. Following this, the design methodology for the proposed bridgeless converter-based charger is outlined, covering key aspects such as circuit design, component selection, and control strategies.

Simulation results are presented to validate the theoretical analysis, followed by experimental evaluations to demonstrate the practical performance of the system.

II. PROPOSED MODEL AND WORKING

Figure 1 is showing proposed design model battery charger for electric vehicle application. The entire block name is mentioned in the present model.

Figure 1:
Propo

The operation of proposed modified converter over complete switching cycle and during the respective half of the mains voltage is presented. The operating principle during positive half cycle is explained as follows.

Mode P-I (t_0-t_1): During positive half cycle of mains voltage, the converter operation begins with mode P-I. The switch SP , connected in upper line, is in ON condition and the inductor Lop starts charging. During this instant, intermediate DC link capacitor, Co discharges through the isolated converter connected at the load side. However, the high frequency diode, $D1$ has no conducting path during this period, due to the stored charge in the inductor and hence, contains a reverse bias voltage across it.

Mode P-II (t_1-t_2): The high frequency diode, $D1$ operates in mode P-II, when the gate pulse to the switch is prevented. The inductor, Lop finds a path, to discharge through it. The

DC link capacitor, Co starts charging and the flyback converter at the output, is supplied for each switching cycle. *Mode P-III (t_2-t_3):* In mode P-III operation, the stored charge in inductor Lop is depleted completely at the end of switching cycle. The inductor current becomes discontinuous for the rest of the switching cycle. During this time, the output power is delivered by the intermediate DC link capacitor, discharging through the path.

The proposed modified converter follows the same switching sequence for the lower switch Sn , inductor, Lon and diode, $D2$ in negative half cycle of mains voltage, the switching sequence for the components operating in different modes during complete input voltage cycle and switching cycle of proposed converter.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of proposed work is based on the following sub-module-

- AC grid
- Modified Converter
- Control Unit
- Battery

The proposed bridgeless converter is shown with topologies. As compared to the other (bridgeless) BL converters based on buck-boost configuration, the proposed converter has the significant advantage of comparable number of total components. The proposed converter has reduced number of conducting components in the current path thereby reducing the system cost and losses. Besides, its PF correction capability is seen to be more improved than the previously developed (bridgeless) BL buck boost and DBR fed converter. Moreover, the main drawback of BL buck-boost converter is the excessive EMI noise emission, which is achieved by proposed converter.

Therefore, the proposed improved bridgeless converter is considered as a better alternative for PFC solution of proposed EV charger. The performance of proposed BL converter-based charger is also compared with

- 1) Conventional converter-based EV charger, which is having a bridge rectifier for PFC at its front end.
- 2) Conventional EV charger, which comprises of only DBR and Flyback converter.

AC Grid

An electrical grid is an interconnected system for conveying electricity from makers to shoppers.

It comprises of creating stations that produce electrical power, high voltage transmission lines that convey power

from far off sources to request focuses, and dissemination lines that interface singular customers.

Modified Converter

This work proposes a grid interface converter to be applied in Vitality Control-Center (ECC) so as to interface dc factors, for example, battery vitality storage framework and AC regular utility grid. Such power electronics arrangement ensures:

Figure 2: BL-Modified converter

- (i) Power stream among DC and AC converter sides,
- (ii) Autonomous control in the two sides,
- (iii) Significant level of incorporation, and
- (iv) Execution of two capacities utilizing a one-of-a-kind power transformation organize.

This work manages the structure and execution of another charger for a battery-worked electric vehicle (EV) with power factor improvement at the front end. In the proposed arrangement, the traditional diode converter at the source end of existing EV battery charger is disposed of with the adjusted power factor correction (PFC) converter. The PFC converter is followed by a flyback secluded converter, which yields the EV battery control to charge it, first in constant current mode at that point switching to constant voltage mode. The proposed PFC converter is controlled utilizing single detected substance to accomplish the vigorous guideline of dc-interface voltage just as to guarantee the solidarity power factor activity.

Flyback Converter

A flyback converter with a yield voltage of 65V, is intended to give the segregation to the battery just as to control the charging current in two charging modes. The determination of ideal switch rating and the charging inductance L mag, are the critical criteria for the flyback converter.

Pulse Width Modulation

Pulse Width Modulation technique is a fixed dc input voltage is given to the converters and a controlled AC yield voltage is gotten by modifying the on and off times of the converter segments. This is the most prominent technique for controlling the yield voltage and in this strategy is known as pulse width modulation.

Control Unit

A correlation investigation of proposed converter encouraged charger and traditional DBR nourished charger with and without PFC, is given.

In this unique situation, various bridgeless converter dependent on double lift setups, are talked about. Regardless of offering the upside of high effectiveness at high power level and improved warm pressure, (bridgeless) BL support topology experiences the confinement of high electromagnetic interference clamor and complex control. Also, the lift converter has the obligation cycle variety point of confinement to control the middle of the road DC-connect voltage at lower supply voltage. Along these lines, a group of bridgeless front-end buck-support converters is given their application to give wide scope of variety in input voltage.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The implementation of the proposed algorithm is done over MATLAB 9.4 The control signal processing toolbox helps us to use the functions available in MATLAB Library for various methods.

Figure 3: Output of Ac source voltage and current
 Figure 3 presents output of source voltage is 260V and 10A current.

Figure 4: Switching pulses of BL-PFC control unit

Figure 5: Voltage and current of capacitor Cn

Figure 6: Voltage of Lop

Figure 7: Battery discharge characteristic
Figure 7 shows nominal current discharge characteristic graph between voltage and time. It is clear that battery discharge at 5.30 Hours.

Figure 8: Performance of Battery

Figure 9: Battery output current

Figure 8 and 9 is showing output performance of battery. Here it can be seen that state of charge of battery is 95% and voltage is 338.25V and current is 33A.

Table 1: Simulation Parameter

Sr. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Peak Voltage amplitude (AC Grid)	260V
2	Frequency	60Hz
Battery Parameter		
3	Nominal voltage	330 V
4	Capacity	6.5Ah
5	State of charge	95%
6	Battery type	Nickel- metal- Hydride

Table 2: Result Comparison

Sr No.	Parameter	Previous Model	Proposed Model
1	Number of components	More	Less
2	Control (with PFC)	Voltage Follower	Voltage Follower
3	Control (Battery)	Simple (dual PI)	Simple (dual PI)
4	Power factor	0.88	0.92

V. CONCLUSION

A modified battery charger with improved power factor followed by a flyback converter has been proposed, analyzed, and validated. The peak load efficiency of 95% is achieved with this modified charger. The design and control of the proposed EV charger in DCM mode have offered the advantage of reduced number of sensors at the output. Moreover, the proposed converter has reduced the input and output current ripples due to inductors both in input and output of the converter. The power factor achieves the significant improvement rather than the previous work. Therefore, the proposed modified battery chargers are more reliable.

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